

P 10b **Report on the Status and Plans of the International Committee on Future Accelerators**

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Over the past years a series of informal meetings has been held by small groups of high energy physicists from the Soviet Union and the Dubna member states, from Western Europe and from the USA in order to discuss the future of high energy physics and questions of international collaboration. The series began with meetings between European and Soviet physicists emerging from the CERN-Dubna and CERN-Serpukhov Collaborations; it was then extended to include USA physicists. Meetings were held in 1967 in Riga, then in 1968 in Semmering, in 1969 in Tbilisi and in 1971 in Morges.

No further meeting in that series was held until March 1975 when a seminar was held in New Orleans entitled "Prospectives in High Energy Physics." The meeting was international in character and presented a forum for discussion of the status of international collaborations in high energy physics as well as for the planning of possible future expansion of those collaborations.

During the course of that meeting it was noted that the progress of high energy physics would almost certainly lead to a requirement for an accelerator and for facilities so large that they would be beyond the reach of any individual nation or any individual region. It was recognized that not only would the technical problems of creating such a facility be enormous, but also that the organizational, economic and political problems connected with the formation of an international collaboration would also be formidable. It was agreed that it was not too early to begin to study some of those problems although it was also agreed that such studies should be undertaken in a manner that would not jeopardize nor slow down progress toward the realization of a number of national and regional projects which were already underway or in a planning stage. A time scale of about

ten years was suggested as one within which plans for such a large facility might be developed. The rather unimaginative name, Very Big Accelerator (VBA) was suggested for the new facility. It was agreed that meetings should be organized to study the problems associated with the creation of such a facility.

At New Orleans it was agreed to hold a first organizational meeting at CERN in October, 1975, with the understanding that the main purpose of that meeting would be to establish an agenda for a second meeting which would be held in Serpukhov, in May, 1976. A third meeting might later be held in the United States. It was further agreed that the studies would be initiated with participation from Eastern Europe, Japan, USA, USSR, and Western Europe. Scientific authorities in each of those regions were to be asked to nominate scientists to participate in the study group.

In CERN, in October of 1975, the organizing meeting was attended by V. Yarba representing the USSR; K. Lanius representing other nations of Eastern Europe; J. Adams, M. Conversi, and W. Jentschke representing Western Europe; L. Lederman, K. Strauch, and R. R. Wilson representing the USA; and V. Weisskopf as the Chairman of the New Orleans meeting at which an initial agreement had been reached to proceed with a study problems associated with a VBA.

Official participants in the Serpukhov meeting were: A. Logunov, A. Vassilyev, M. Markov, V. Glukhikh, L. Soloviev, I. Chuvilo, and V. Yarba from the USSR; K. Lanius and V. Dzhelepov representing JINR member states; Y. Yamaguchi from Japan; V. Weisskopf, R. R. Wilson, L. Lederman, M. Barton, R. Diebold and J. Bjorken from the USA; and G. von Dardel, U. Amaldi, D. Husmann, K. Johnsen, A. Rousset, and D. Thomas from CERN member states.

At the Serpukhov meeting the general scale for a VBA was discussed. It was tentatively decided that something equal to or greater than a 10 TeV fixed target accelerator would be the smallest facility appropriately to be considered. It was further decided that a minimum energy of 100 GeV would establish a scale for a pair of e^+e^- storage rings.

In the report of the meeting a set of three conclusions was stated:

A) The present status of the science of the structure of matter poses fundamental problems which require a new generation of facilities. . . Such facilities are within the capabilities of the individual regions and are needed for continued progress of this field of research.

B) The success of regional and interregional collaboration in the past provides a good basis for extending and strengthening this collaboration in the new generation of regional facilities.

C) Looking beyond this new generation of regional accelerators we foresee the need for an accelerator complex (VBA) which will require international collaboration of all regions concerned.

Finally four recommendations were formulated at the Serpukhov meeting:

1. Efforts should be made to coordinate the design and construction of new regional facilities. Consultations and exchange of experiences should be encouraged in order to optimize the diversity of facilities and to enhance the efficiency of construction and operation. The study group also recommends joint studies of new technology (*e. g.*, superconductivity, new detectors and other experimental apparatus) and joint design and/or construction of components of regional projects.

2. Joint utilization of regional facilities by scientists of different regions should be organized on the basis of present and future arrangements or agreements. The general availability of regional installations is essential to enable scientists of different regions to take advantage of facilities with complementary research potentialities.

3. International collaboration should provide for studies leading towards the realization of a next generation of superhigh energy facilities, following the regional projects referred to above. It is expected that these facilities will be so large that their realization will be

possible only by pooling the resources of all regions concerned into common international projects.

Creation of a superhigh energy accelerator complex (VBA) involves especially complicated scientific, technical and organizational problems. These will require several years of continuing studies and discussions. The Study Group recommends that these discussions begin in the near future leading to the start of the design of the VBA in about 10 years.

4. In view of the need for these extensions of international collaboration, the Study Group suggests to the IUPAP Division of Particles and Fields to initiate these activities in an appropriate form, for example, by appointing a sub-committee for the purpose of organizing working groups and future meetings such as the present one.

In response to Recommendation #4, stemming from the Serpukhov meeting, the subject of IUPAP sponsorship of the new study project was placed on the agenda of the meeting of the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields which was held in Tbilisi on July 20, 1976. At that meeting it was agreed that the IUPAP Commission should serve as sponsor of the activities of the proposed new committee which was there officially named the International Committee on Future Accelerators (ICFA).

There was considerable discussion about the appropriate membership of the new Committee and about the charge which would be presented to the new committee by the IUPAP Commission. It was recognized that if the activity was now to be formalized by IUPAP sponsorship, IUPAP must assume a substantial responsibility for the direction in which ICFA might go and for the procedures through which ICFA would operate.

Accordingly at Tbilisi the IUPAP Commission adopted a scheme of representation on the new committee consisting of two members from Western Europe, two members from Eastern Europe, two members from the USA, one member from Japan and the Chairman of the IUPAP Commission, serving in an *ex-officio* capacity, with an explicit responsibility to represent the interests of the "other countries."

Following the Tbilisi meeting certain objections were raised regarding the formula that had been adopted by the IUPAP Commission. In an effort to resolve that problem and in preparation for the first official meeting of ICFA, Bernard Gregory, who was then Chairman of the IUPAP Commission, had a series of discussions with the interested parties. In the course of those discussions, Dr. Gregory formulated a substitute suggestion for ICFA membership which appeared to be generally acceptable. The suggested composition of the committee was: three members from CERN member countries, three from the Soviet Union, three from the USA, one from Japan, and one from Dubna member states other than the Soviet Union. The Chairman of the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields was still designated to be a member, *ex officio*, as before.

During the winter of 1976-77, the IUPAP Commission agreed, by correspondence, on a stipulation of ICFA responsibilities as follows:

"To organize workshops for the study of problems related to an international super high energy accelerator complex (VBA) and to elaborate the framework of its construction and of its use."

"To organize meetings for the exchange of information on future plans of regional facilities and for the formulation of advice on joint studies and uses."

No official IUPAP action on the revised suggestion for ICFA membership was planned to be taken prior to the annual Commission meeting scheduled for August 31, in Hamburg, and since a first meeting of the ICFA Committee had been scheduled to take place on August 30, it was agreed that the scheduled ICFA meeting would be held but would be provisional in character, its official status pending approval, on the next day, by the IUPAP Commission, of the constituency of the ICFA Committee.

For the provisional first meeting of ICFA the membership was as follows: J. Adams, G. von Dardel, and W. Paul from Western Europe; L. Lederman, V. Weisskopf, and R. Wilson from the USA; V. Dzhelepov, K. Mishnekov and V. Yarba from the USSR; K. Lanis from the Dubna member states; Y. Yamaguchi from "Other Countries" (Japan); and B.

Gregory, *ex officio*, as Chairman of the IUPAP Commission. A. Rousset, of France, also attended as Committee Secretary.

At this first provisional meeting of ICFA Bernard Gregory, chairman of the IUPAP Commission, was elected to serve also as Chairman of ICFA. At his request, A. Rousset was appointed to assist him in his task. Gregory presented the stipulation of ICFA responsibilities, as formulated by the IUPAP Commission and as stated above. The ICFA members proposed to interpret those instructions as being identical to the more detailed recommendations which had been forthcoming from the organizing meeting at Serpukhov. Those recommendations placed more emphasis on the coordination of present regional activities and somewhat less emphasis on activities specifically oriented toward the study and organization of the VBA. Gregory was asked to report on that point to the IUPAP Commission.

At the provisional ICFA meeting it was also decided to create a "Regional Facilities Collaboration Study Group" (Group 1). That Group was to deal with problems of collaboration on design, construction and use of all accelerators.

It was further decided to create a "Super High Energy Facility Study Group" (Group 2). That study group was to cover all scientific, technical and organizational problems pertaining to a super high energy accelerator (VBA).

Questions were raised during the discussion regarding the possible existence of limits on design parameters of very high energy machines. To address those questions, it was decided that Group 2 should hold a seminar on "Technical Possibilities and Limitations of Accelerators and Detectors" at Fermilab in the middle of 1978.

In order to set up the two study groups, three members of the ICFA Committee (Adams, Wilson and Yarba) were nominated to send proposals on terms of reference, working methods, topics, agendas and memberships to Gregory before 31 October 1977. A final decision was to be taken by exchange of telex or by a meeting in January of 1978 at CERN.

Finally it was agreed that an ICFA meeting

should be held during the next International Conference on High Energy Physics at Tokyo (24-30 August, 1978). It was agreed that a report of ICFA activities should be made at that conference.

On the day following the first provisional meeting of ICFA, described above, the IUPAP Commission met in Hamburg and approved the revised membership of the ICFA Committee, thus officially constituting the prior day's meeting as the first meeting of ICFA. There was an extended discussion of the preferences that had been expressed by ICFA members concerning the charge under which ICFA would operate. However the IUPAP Commission retained its previous statement of ICFA responsibilities, preferring to maintain a strong emphasis on a VBA rather than on the coordination of the design, construction and use of regional facilities. The IUPAP Commission did favor an organized exchange of information about the progress and plans of regional facilities, but the members believed that to be covered in the second part of their charge to ICFA.

Since the IUPAP Commission has the tradition of meeting on an annual basis, it was agreed that a report should be submitted by the ICFA Committee to the IUPAP Commission each year, at the latter's regular meeting.

Last autumn and winter, Gregory, working together with Rousset, was making preparations for a second meeting of ICFA at CERN in January. Then, at Christmas time, Bernard Gregory's sudden and tragic death ended his brilliant and dedicated career. He was a man of great talent and unusual insight. He had a deep commitment to the furthering of international cooperation. He was a principal moving force behind the initiative that was taken at New Orleans. Without his leadership, tact and diplomacy no agreement could have been reached, and his guidance and judgment will be missed in the ICFA enterprise as it has been and will be in many other activities which are important both to high energy physics and to France. The most fitting tribute we can pay to him will be to assure that his dream of increasing international cooperation flourishes.

After Gregory's death, Larkin Kerwin, Secretary General of IUPAP, asked me, as

Secretary of the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields, to assume responsibility for the remainder of Gregory's term as Chairman. As Acting Chairman of that Commission, I also became the IUPAP ex-officio member of ICFA, and with that, temporarily assumed Gregory's elected position as Chairman of ICFA.

I immediately contacted Andre Rousset and we began putting together the pieces that he and Gregory had been working on in preparation for an ICFA Meeting in January. Our first task was to arrange for replacements for three of the original ICFA members who had submitted their resignations. A von Dardel and W. Paul had submitted resignations by reason of the fact that their respective terms as Chairman of ECFA and as Chairman of the CERN Science Policy Committee had expired. Leon Van Hove, the designated responsible authority for Western European representation, recommended M. Vivargent and G. Stafford, successors to von Dardel's and Paul's previous responsibilities, as replacement members of ICFA. A mail ballot to the IUPAP Commission Membership obtained unanimous agreement to those two suggested appointments.

Last winter I also regretfully received Victor Weisskopf's resignation from ICFA. Although he expressed his continuing enthusiasm for the project, he indicated that he was no longer able to undertake the strenuous travel that would be involved. The vacancy created by Dr. Weisskopf's resignation was only filled a few days ago when, by action of the IUPAP Commission, B. Richter was appointed to fill that vacancy in the U. S. representation.

At the IUPAP Commission meeting in Hamburg the Commission had expressed its wish that its Chairman should serve on ICFA only in an ex officio capacity and should not normally have a position of responsibility on the ICFA Committee. The Chairman of ICFA was to be elected annually by action of the ICFA Committee from among its directly appointed members. Accordingly, prior to the January ICFA Meeting, I informed Committee members that I was withdrawing my name from consideration for the ICFA chairmanship.

In Hamburg, the IUPAP Commission **had**

Table I.

Name and (location) of project	Particles	Energy (GeV in c.m.)	Luminosity ($\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Other options	Status and/or dates
PETRA (DESY)	e^-e^+	38	10^{32} at 30 GeV	—	Starting operation \sim 1980 Depends on tests of superconducting cavities in 1979 (CERN-DESY- KARLSRUHE)
	—	45	1.5×10^{32} at 38 GeV	—	
	—	> 60	$\sim 10^{31}$	—	
PEP (SLAC)	—	8-36	10^{32} at 30 GeV	ep and/or increase energy to 48 GeV	\sim Oct. 79
CESR (Cornell)	—	16-20	10^{32}	—	1979 Completion
ALA (Frascati)	—	2.4	$2 \times 10^{30} \sim 2 \times 10^{31}$	—	Approved for construction starting 1979
LEP (CERN)	—	80-200	$\sim 10^{32}$ max	ep if LEP is close to SPS Polarized beams	Design study under way-project not yet approved After PETRA has run DESY will study 2×100 GeV possibility DESY-CERN will coordinate on single project
(DESY)	—	—	—	—	

empowered me, as Secretary, to provide for a rotation of terms on the ICFA Committee, based on a three year cycle. Terms are normally to start on January 1 of any given year and to end on December 31. Individual members will be eligible for reappointment for a second term, but normally will not be eligible for appointment for a third term.

The present ICFA membership together with the dates of termination of present appointments is as follows:

Adams (1979)	Dzhelepov (1979)
Vivargent (1980)	Mishnekov (1980)
Stafford (1981)	Yarba (1981)
Lederman (1979)	Lanius (1980)
Richter (1980)	Yamaguchi (1979)
R. R. Wilson (1981)	Goldwasser (1978)
	(<i>ex officio</i> as Acting Chairman of IUPAP)

The second meeting of ICFA convened at CERN on the 27th of January, 1978. The first order of business was the election of a new ICFA Chairman, and John Adams was unanimously chosen.

At that meeting it was decided to accept the stipulation of ICFA responsibilities as formulated by the IUPAP Commission. It was further agreed that there was no need, at

the present time, to set up standing working groups as had been suggested at the previous meeting in Hamburg. However it was agreed that there was a clear need to organize a number of workshops on topics related to an eventual VBA Project and on topics related both to existing regional facilities and to the realization of a VBA. It was agreed that there were four main areas of interest relating to the VBA.

1. The physics needs.
2. Accelerator possibilities and limitations.
3. Detector possibilities and limitations.
4. How to build and use a VBA.

It was agreed to organize a first workshop on "Possibilities and Limitations of Particle Accelerators and Detectors" at Fermilab from October 9-19, 1978. It was further agreed that there should be about forty participants in all, ten each to be designated by the three major regions, two from Japan and the others to be chosen by the workshop's Organizing Committee to round out the technical competence of the group. Fermilab was asked to take responsibility for the organization of the workshop. It was agreed that a meeting of ICFA, itself, should be held in conjunction with the Fermilab workshop and that there was no need

Table II.

Name and (location) of project	Particles	Energy (GeV)		Luminosity ($\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) or intensity	Other options	Status and/or dates
Tristan (KEK)	ep	15 ^e	50-200 ^p	$6-9 \times 10^{31}$	e^+e^- pp 400 GeV (supercond.)	None approved
Cheep (CERN SPS)	—	25	270	5×10^{31}	Trade off energy and luminosity	
Proper (DESY PETRA)	—	10	175	4×10^{32}		
LEP Option (CERN)	—	17	280	1×10^{32}		
Fermilab	—	60	400	6×10^{31}	—	
		12	1000	10^{32}		

for an ICFA meeting at the time of the Tokyo Conference.

It was tentatively agreed to hold a second workshop on "Superconducting Magnets and Cavities" at IHEP, Serpukhov, in the Spring of 1979. A final decision whether or not to hold this workshop will be made at the next meeting of the full ICFA Committee which will follow the workshop at Fermilab on October 20, 1978.

The question of whether or not to hold a workshop on the physics needs for a VBA, perhaps also in 1979, will be discussed at the next ICFA Meeting.

It was agreed that there were three topics of interest related to the current regional facilities; (1) the physics reasons for building the new regional facilities such as LEP, UNK, ISABELLE, etc., (2) the technology required for building these regional facilities and (3) the experience gained in the present joint utilization of regional facilities.

Finally, it was agreed that I should report on ICFA activities at the Tokyo High Energy Physics Conference. That I am doing today.

Plans are proceeding well toward the convening of a workshop in October at Fermilab. The Organizing Committee consists of Lee Teng, Chairman; Jack Sandweiss, Associate Chairman; Burt Richter, Jim Sanford and Bill Willis. The meeting is to start on October 15 and extend through October 21. One concern of the workshop will be with problems related to various types of accelerators and accelerator configurations, —technical limitations, approximate cost, and so forth. The second concern of the workshop will be with problems relating to detector designs, capabili-

ties and limitations.

My own term on IUPAP expires next month and with it will expire my membership on ICFA. I believe now, as I did at New Orleans, that the concept of an international laboratory is one which must be developed with inspiration and nurtured with wisdom. Its role in the future development of high energy physics and its role in the development of a new dimension of international collaboration could both be of enormous importance.

The problems are sufficiently difficult that they will be met only if the need for such a laboratory is a real one. That condition will be satisfied only if the scope of the laboratory, the dimensions of the facility and the cost of the construction and operation are such that they require a world collaboration.

The time scale on which the physics demand for such a facility will become pressing is likely to be about a decade. That time scale might lead some to an attitude of complacency and inaction. However the problems are so complex that if we are to know how to start to address them, even ten years from now, we must begin to try to understand them immediately.

We are not likely to choose the design of a VBA today or tomorrow. But it is not too early to try to understand the physics needs, the technical limitations and the economic and political problems. I am sure that you will all join in wishing your IUPAP and ICFA representatives the best of luck in pursuing this dream.

In closing I cannot help remembering Steve Weinberg's closing remarks this morning when he expressed his hope that today's outstanding

Table III.

Name and (location) of project	Particles	Energy (GeV)	Luminosity (cm ⁻² s ⁻¹) or intensity	Other options	Status and/or dates
$\bar{p}p$ (CERN)	$\bar{p}p$	540	10 ³⁰		Under construction '78-'81
Tevatron (Fermilab)	p	1000	5 × 10 ¹³ ppp		"
	pp	1000 on 250	4 × 10 ³⁰		"
	$\bar{p}p$	250 on 250	2 × 10 ²⁸		electron cooling experiment in progress
Isabelle	$\bar{p}p$	1000 on 1000	10 ³⁰		"
	pp	400 on 400	~ 5 × 10 ³²	$\bar{p}\bar{p}$ ep	Construction starts 1979 Completion ~ 1986
Institute for High Energy Physics (Peking)	p	50	1-2 × 10 ¹³ ppp	Booster could increase intensity (Phase 2 ? TeV)	'78-'83 '84-'89
UNK (Serpukhov)	p	3000	6 × 10 ¹⁴ ppp	$\bar{p}\bar{p}$	Development started-
	pp	2100 + 1100	10 ³²		construction not yet approved
Tristan (KEK)	pp	200 + 200	10 ³⁴	$\bar{p}\bar{p}$ or 400+400 (supercond.)	Not yet approved

questions might all be answered by the time of the next conference, but also his doubt that we would be so skillful or lucky, I join him on both counts, and, in that connection, I would like to share with you the only great disappointment I have had at this conference.

From the Eight-fold Way we are all used to relying on the teachings of Buddha for our insights in elementary particle physics. It therefore was with some pleasure and anticipation that I roused through the book on the Teachings of Buddha which I found in my hotel room. As I hastily scanned the pages it was not long before I thought I had found exactly what I had half expected. I thought I read:

Search For Truth

In the search for truth there are certain questions that are important.

Of what material is the universe constructed?

Is the universe eternal?

Are there limits or not to the universe?

In what way is this human society put together?

What is the ideal form of organization for human society?

Reading this I was gratified to find this ringing support for the pursuit of political science,

sociology, cosmology, and high energy physics.

You can then imagine my shock when I went back to read the passage more carefully. What it really says, by way of introduction, is:

"In the search for truth there are certain questions that are unimportant."

And in concluding that passage, the Teachings go on to say:

"If a man were to postpone his searching and practicing for Enlightenment until such questions were solved, he would die before he found the path."

Let us hope that not all of us will die before we take at least a few more steps along the path for which we are searching.

The report I was originally requested to present at this conference was supposed only to inform you about the birth, purpose and progress of a new committee which is intended to represent you and to concern itself primarily with problems pertaining to the long range future for the study of high energy physics. At first I had doubts that such a report would be useful, but, in light of the many questions I have been asked, during this conference, about the letters ICFA which appear at this point in the program, it is clear that not much is known about this new com-

mittee and that even less is known about its activities.

Some of my friends have suggested that perhaps ICFA stands for International Conference for Future Administrators, a possibility that might concern me as I leave Fermilab. However, in fact, it stands for International Committee on Future Accelerators and I shall tell you more about it in a few moments.

First, however, some of you may remember that in one of the earlier Conference Programs there was listed a session on Future Facilities. That session has been cancelled but during the first few days of the Conference, coincident with the parallel sessions an International Symposium on Future Perspectives in High

Energy Physics was held. At its conclusion a summary of the projects which had been described was presented by Professor Nishikawa. I have been asked to fill in some of the cancelled plenary session by summarizing the substance of last week's Symposium. The following three transparencies are taken mostly from Dr. Nishikawa. They summarize the states of short-range future accelerator projects and provide a bridge of reality to the ICFA dream which I shall describe in the few minutes.

So much for the world of reality and perhaps a little beyond, I would now like to step into the world of pure dreams.

P11: Concluding Talk

Chairman: G. TAKEDA

Speaker: Y. NAMBU

Scientific Secretaries: J. ARAFUNE
M. YOSHIMURA

(Wednesday, August 30, 1978; 14: 30–15: 30)